

PHILOLOGICAL SCIENCES

ACTIVITIES FOR TEACHING LISTENING: TEACHING TO LISTEN AS A COMMUNICATIVE SKILL

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Abstract

We know that listening is more than just hearing words. So, listening as an active process whereby students receive, construct meaning from, and respond to spoken messages. Before we can develop appropriate assessment techniques for listening, we must first understand the nature of listening. Two models of listening have been identified in the literature: bottom-up and top-down approaches. The authors tried to explain how to approach to listening assessment and they shows activities for teaching listening. Here were given general versus of academic listening, considerations in designing listening tasks, background knowledge and test content.

Keywords: academic listening, knowledge, attitude, emphasis

The assessment of listening abilities is one of the least developed, yet one of the most important areas of language testing and assessment, In fact, Nunan calls listening comprehension “the poor cousin amongst the various language skills”. [1, p.89]

As teachers we recognize the importance of teaching and then assessing the listening skills of our students, but-for a number of reasons- we are often unable to do this effectively. One reason for this is that the listening process is internal and not subject to direct study and observation. To learn to speak students first must learn to understand the spoken language they hear. In the past, educators hypothesized that listening was a passive skill because it could not be observed. In more recent theoretical models, listening is regarded as an active process. Another reason for the past neglect of the listening skill was that the productive skills of writing and speaking were emphasized. In recent years, however, the position on this has changed, and now a much greater emphasis is placed on listening.

Mr. Wright knows that listening is more than just hearing words. She views listening as an active process whereby students receive, construct meaning from, and respond to spoken messages. Because she sees listening as an integral part of the communication process, she is careful not to neglect this important skill. Some of the things she does in order to ensure valid and reliable listening assessment are:

- *she consults her specifications before starting the listening test development process

- *she uses a variety of assessment tasks with different listening purposes

- *she collects authentic material to use for listening scripts, and so on. [2, p.90]

We have identified three major approaches to the assessment of listening abilities; discrete point, integrative and communicative approaches.

The discrete point approach became popular during the 1950s with the advent of audio-lingual method. This approach broke listening into component elements

and assessed them separately. Some of the common question types in this approach included phonemic discrimination, paraphrase recognition, and response evaluation. The underlying rationale for the discrete-point approach stemmed from two beliefs; that it was important to be able to isolate one element of language from a continuous stream of speech and that spoken language was believed to be the same as written language, only presented orally.

The integrative approach started in the early 1970s. The underlying rationale for this approach is best explained by Oller. [3]:”Whereas discrete items attempt to test knowledge of language one bit at a time, integrative tests attempt to assess a learners capacity to use many bits at the same time. Proponents of the integrative approach to listening assessment believed that the whole of language is greater than the sum of its parts. Common question types in this approach were dictation and cloze.

The communicative approach arose at approximately the same time as the integrative approach as a result of the communication language teaching movement. In this approach, the listener must be able to comprehend the message and then use it in context. Communicative question formats should be authentic in nature.

General versus Academic Listening

Unlike foreign and second language listening in a conversational setting, a major part of listening in a university context involves lecture comprehension. Many observers have noted differences between general listening and academic listening. In some cases, these differences have important implications for testing.

Early work by Richards separated general and academic listening on a taxonomy of micro-skills.[4, p.92] Richards taxonomy identified 33 skills involved to general listening as well as 18 academic listening micro-skills.

Considerations in designing listening tasks

Before attempting to design a listening test, teachers should consult the course objectives and the listening test specifications that will provide information about objectives, formats and themes. The tasks should reflect those that occur in real-life situations, and the language used should be natural. As always the students should be able to use background knowledge to make sense of the test tasks and items. The primary focus of items should generally be on meaning rather than on form.

Background or prior knowledge needs to be taken into account because research suggests that background knowledge affects comprehension and test performance. However, take care to ensure that students are not able to answer test questions based on their background knowledge rather than on their comprehension.

Testers can control for background knowledge in one of three ways. First, test designers can ensure students have an equal amount of background knowledge by writing listening tests that exploit specific course materials. Second, they can provide students with the requisite background knowledge during testing via advanced organizers or practice prompts. Third, test writers can use topics that are unfamiliar to the entire student population. In any case, an attempt to standardize the presence or absence of background knowledge should be made in any listening text that purports to be a valid indicator of comprehension.

The test specification might provide you with information about the following:

- *text types (narrative, descriptive, etc.)
- *speech types to be used (phrases, single utterances, two person dialogues, multi-participant dialogue, monologues)
- *mode of input (audio, video, live reader)
- *varieties of English to be used
- *scripted or unscripted input
- *length of input (in time or number of exchanges for dialogues)

Some teachers feel that the unavailability of suitable texts is listening comprehensions most pressing issue because creating scripts that have the characteristics of oral language is not an easy task. In desperation, teachers take a reading text and transform it into a listening script, resulting in contrived and inauthentic listening tasks because written texts often lack the redundant features that are so important in helping us understand speech. A better strategy is to look for texts you like and then infuse oral characteristics into them.

Start by doing an inventory of the topics in a course and collect appropriate material well in advance of exam construction. Some strategies to help you infuse oral characteristics into reading texts are:

*Insert as oral marker at the beginning: "Today I am going to talk about..."

*Spoken language typically uses less complex structures than written text, so change complex sentences into shorter ones.

*Insert devices that help you buy time to plan what to say next (pauses and fillers like um, err, ah)

*use coordinating conjunctions like and, but, or so instead of ones like although and whereas

*read about what you have written to see if it sounds natural.

*If you work from a recording, make a tape script. If you work from a tape script, make a recording.

*Build in pausing, redundancy, and other features of oral texts (false starts, ungrammatically, hesitations)[3]

Whenever possible try to use samples of authentic speech to assess listening. Other good sources include radio, television, pre-recorded teaching materials, pod casts, internet, and teacher-produced materials.

As researchers, we recommend that student have to know between 90-95 percent of the words to understand a text/script. Indeed the level of vocabulary that you utilize in your scripts can affect the difficulty and hence the comprehension of students. If your institution employs word lists, it is recommended that you seed vocabulary from your own word lists, into listening scripts whenever possible.

Item writing

Once you have decided on the texts and formats you are going to use, it is time to think about the individual test items. Listen to the passage and note areas you want students to understand from the input text. When you have done this, you are ready to start constructing items. Place test items sufficiently far apart in the test so that students have time to respond to one item without missing the next. For example, if answers fall too closely together in the text, students can miss one and fine themselves listening for responses that have long since passed.

Frame each new section with an advance organizer to help develop the context and activate students background knowledge. These examples prepare students for the listening texts:

Task 1: Listen to the interview with Dr. Peter Davidson, a specialist in sports medicine. He will give you his views on the advantages and disadvantages of extreme sports. Then answer the questions.

Task 2. Mr. and Mrs. Rollins, a young couple from New York City, are discussing their summer plans. Listen to their conversation and then answer the questions.

If you are using a script, build in and record specific instructions so that students know exactly how long they have for each step. This following is a sample of pre-recorded instructions for a listening test.

You have one minute to read the questions.
Now start listening.
Student hear task 1 recording
You have 1 minute to read the questions.
Student hear task 1 recording
You have 30 minutes to write your answer
Now listen again
Students hear task 1 again

The length of listening test is generally determined by one of two things: the length of the tape or the number of repetitions of the texts. Most published listening tests do not require attention to timing. The proctor simply inserts the tape or CD into the machine, and the test is over when a pre-recorded. This is the end of the listening test statement is played. For teacher-produced

listening tests, the timing of the test will usually be determined by how many times the test-takers are permitted to hear each passage. Proficiency tests like the TOEFL and IELTS allow students to hear the listening input passages one time, whereas achievement tests usually repeat the input twice. Buck recommends that if you are assessing main idea, input should be heard twice.[4] According to Carrol, listening tests should not exceed 30 minutes.[5]

Remember to give students time to pre-read the questions before the test and answer the questions throughout the test. If students are required to transfer their answer from the test paper to an answer sheet, extra time to do this should be built into the exam.

Conclusion

Valid and reliable testing of listening comprehension is a complex process. The teachers should keep these points in mind:

1. Reading texts must be converted to listening texts.

A written text lacks oral features. The closer a text is to oral language, the more appropriate it will be to assess students listening comprehension.

2. Give credit for what students know

Don't deduct for spelling or grammar mistakes when your focus is on listening comprehension.

3. Don't forget the importance of background knowledge

Because students do not have multiple passes at the text, there needs to be sufficient contextualization prior to listening. To facilitate schema activation, set the context of the listening in the instructions.

4. Don't just test what is easy to test

Many teachers focus their test items on local information (e.g. numbers, dates, places) because these detail-focused items are easier to write than items that focus on meaning. Make sure your major focus is on meaning. Include higher-order thinking skills as well.

5. Don't expect full comprehension

Teachers should not expect students to remember everything they hear: students often comprehend without being able to remember content.

6. Accept that skill contamination will occur.

In a perfect world, reading would never interfere with the assessment of the listening skill. In reality, the successful completion of practically every listening test requires competent in other language skill areas. However, if the aim is to test listening, students should not be asked to read or write too much.

7. Assess all types of listening (top down/ bottom up and general /academic)

Vary your measures where listening comprehension is concerned.

8. Don't forget the cornerstones of good testing practice.

In listening, as in all the other skills, teachers should be guided by the cornerstones of testing; validity, reliability, practicality, washback, authenticity, transparency and security.

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